

S₄ once over easy

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In a previous article [1] the 24-element symmetric group S₄ was derived through Kronecker evolution of S₂, and a heuristic 'fill-the-gap' procedure. Thus, given the two elements of S₂

$$s_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad s_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Kronecker products evolved the 'parents' of S₄; in OCTAVE notation:

$$\text{kron}(s_0, s_1) = p7, \quad \text{kron}(s_1, s_0) = p16, \quad \text{kron}(s_0, s_0) = p0, \quad \text{kron}(s_1, s_1) = p23$$

The parent matrices are

$$p0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad p7 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad p16 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad p23 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Now, an unique shorthand is available - called here a 'tag' - to represent any symmetric group matrix, a pointer tracking the column location of '1' as rows increase; for the parents

$$t0 = 1234 \quad t7 = 2143 \quad t16 = 3412 \quad t23 = 4321$$

Below is the OCTAVE code to produce any tag - t7 in particular, given the matrix p7

```
for k=1:4,t7(k)=find(p7(k,:)==1);end
```

To recover matrix p7 from tag t7 do

```
for k=1:4,p7(k,t7(k))=1;end
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Thus there is a one-to-one correspondence between tags and their (0,1) matrices. Moreover, tags have unique complements, in the sense that the two sum to the string '5555', in the case of S₄; the table below collates results for the 24 elements - parents are in light blue.

elem	comp	elem	comp
p0 1234	p23 4321	p1 2134	p22 3421
p6 1243	p17 4312	p7 2143	p16 3412
p2 1324	p21 4231	p4 2314	p19 3241
p12 1342	p11 4213	p18 2341	p5 3214
p8 1423	p15 4132	p10 2413	p13 3142
p14 1432	p9 4123	p20 2431	p3 3124

As noted earlier [1], the four matrices p0, p7, p16, and p23 add up to a matrix of all 1's. The parent tag matrix

$$U = [t0;t7;t16;t23] = \begin{pmatrix} 1234 \\ 2143 \\ 3412 \\ 4321 \end{pmatrix}$$

will now be used to generate the remaining 20 elements of S_4 through column-swap operations, replacing heuristics with OCTAVE code. To swap column j with k, do

$$U(:,[j \ k]) = U(:,[k \ j])$$

There are $nchoosek(4,2) = 6$ column-pair swaps available here, resulting in 24 elements, though half are duplicates. Still, double-column swapping comes to the rescue; the table below has final results.

U	1↔2	1↔3	1↔4	1↔2→2↔3	1↔2→2↔4
1234 = t0	2134 = t1	3214 = t5	4231 = t21	2314 = t4	2431 = t20
2143 = t7	1243 = t6	4123 = t9	3142 = t13	1423 = t8	1342 = t12
3412 = t16	4312 = t17	1432 = t14	2413 = t10	4132 = t15	4213 = t11
4321 = t23	3421 = t22	2341 = t18	1324 = t2	3241 = t19	3124 = t3

Notice each swapping has generated complement pairs, color-coded for comparison; and the matrices corresponding to the tag foursomes in each column add up to the matrix of all 1's, just like the Kronecker parents themselves. Thus column-swapping did indeed 'fill-the-gaps'!

Now, a simpler parent matrix composed of rows permuting cyclically the tag 1234 also works; thus

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} 1234 \\ 2341 \\ 3412 \\ 4123 \end{pmatrix}$$

yields the remaining 20 tags through single-column swaps:

U	1↔2	1↔3	1↔4	2↔3	3↔4
1234 = t0	2134 = t1	3214 = t5	4231 = t21	1324 = t2	1243 = t6
2341 = t18	3241 = t19	4321 = t23	1342 = t12	2431 = t20	2314 = t4
3412 = t16	4312 = t17	1432 = t14	2413 = t10	3142 = t13	3421 = t22
4123 = t9	1423 = t8	2143 = t7	3124 = t3	4213 = t11	4132 = t15

The plotted tag sequence below shows a step-wise pattern, though nothing else obviously predictable; and the plotted first difference sheds no additional light.

Reference

[1] 'Spawning S_4 from Kronecker products', <https://zenodo.org/records/10452481>